

INFORMATION PAPER
UNIDENTIFIED ANOMALOUS PHENOMENA
AWARENESS AND STRATEGIC RESPONSE

21 January 2025

Authors: Sean Grosvenor, Keith Taylor Sr., Ed.D, Joshua S. Pierson, MS, DSS

Subject: Discuss proposed protocol for training, tactical, operational, and strategic response to reported Unidentified Anomalous Phenomena (UAP) encounters.

1. **Purpose:** This paper seeks to outline the current state of UAP response protocol and provide a foundational structure for conducting UAP response activities.

2. **Discussion:**

A. **The Problem**

Current UAP incident response activities are not standardized across organizations conducting UAP research and investigations. Each organization has a particular operational procedure which often leads to a degradation of validation for UAP encounters, effective case management, and a loss of evidence chain of custody. Furthermore, the absence of standardizing UAP response diminishes global analytical efforts to determine the capabilities, motive, and intent of possible Non-Human Intelligence (NHI) associated with the technological attributes of UAP.

B. **Key Outcomes**

- 1) Better fidelity of data collection and analysis will guide investigations to decrease the potential for misidentification of UAP.
- 2) Collaboration among organizations, investigators, and analysts will improve comprehensive understanding of the nature and implications of UAP encounters.
- 3) UAP investigations and research efforts adhering to standardized data collection, analysis and conclusions, will improve strategic response to reported UAP/NHI encounters.

C. **UAP Investigative Response Methodology**

- 1) Approaching UAP inquiries requires a standardized training¹ data collection and categorization model which presents opportunities for oversight and replication of the process. Understanding three primary principles of UAP response is critical to the implementation of the response model:
 - UAP response organizations must adhere to legal doctrine for testimonial, demonstrative, and physical evidence. Failure to adhere to validation guidelines compromises the quality of conclusions derived from information and evidence assessment.

¹ Taylor Sr. Ed.D, Keith, Ivan Hannel, Esq., and Sean Grosvenor. "A New Challenge: UAP Awareness and Response Training for Public Safety Professionals", February 4, 2025. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14802826>.

- Investigators, scientists, and subject matter experts must be coordinated in the various disciplines associated with reported UAP and NHI encounters. Integrating these elements will increase effective investigative, analytical, and research efforts.
- Information should be assessed by specific academic and professional lines of effort, in the areas of Biology, Psychology, Technology and Sociology. The UAP response organizational model is managed by one individual and a committee of oversight and subject matter professionals that ensure adherence to the established standard operating procedure. Lines of effort are described by the following groups:
 - a) **Biological Group:** Consists of a medical evaluation and forensic analysis team. This group focuses both on establishing if the witness was the victim of a physiological encounter and collecting trace evidence from both the victim and the reported UAP location. This group has subject matter experts from the medical and forensic science professions.
 - b) **Psychological Group:** Gathers information from the witness regarding their encounter. This group includes law enforcement and intelligence professionals with the requisite credentials, psychiatrists and other cognitive specialists. Individuals supporting the collection of testimonial evidence focus on conducting interviews, evaluations, memory recovery, deception detection, and providing emotional support to the witness. The psychological group also categorizes witness types to offer comparative analysis across the spectrum of witnesses.
 - c) **Technological Group:** Conducts data collection from technical devices and analyzes imagery, audio, measurements and signatures, chemical traces, and environmental factors. The protocols established in the technological group form the criteria for physical evidence collection and chain of custody.
 - d) **Sociological Group:** Manages the fusion of UAP response investigations with other analytical efforts and produces all-source analytical results. It collaborates with external organizations to share information, investigative and analytical efforts, and develops publications for public awareness relative to UAP investigations.

2) Information-Gathering and Analysis Process

The process of conducting UAP response investigations begins with an observer witnessing, or a technical device collecting data from, an anomalous event. The organization then dispatches an investigations team that has analytical and subject matter expert support. The team collects the evidence and conducts interviews. Upon completion of the inquiry, the team authors three reports: an operational report, which captures the interview narrative and a detailed description of evidence; an inventory report documenting the chain of custody for all collected evidence, and an investigative summary which contains a summary of the investigation. The information is then published into subsequent databases. These databases catalog and categorize signatures, sources, and chain of custody. The fusion team, under the sociological group, then analyzes both the sources and the signatures to enhance a UAP profile and the source profile. These analytical efforts then inform future UAP response and proactive deployment of investigations teams.²

² See pp. 249 of “Detectable Signatures of UAP; Building an Intelligence Picture of Capabilities through Structured Analytic Techniques” by Joshua S. Pierson, MS, DSS, located at <https://zenodo.org/records/10982656> (accessed 21 January 2025).

D. Messaging Success

Informing the public on UAP encounters and response efforts requires incorporating two objectives. First, investigations and analyses ultimately seek to address the risk and threat proposition that UAP may pose. Second, understanding the capability and intent of UAP informs future response efforts. Addressing the risk and threat proposition requires classifying UAP encounters into three primary categories contingent upon whether the encounter had a benevolent, malevolent, or benign effect on the witness and the surrounding environment. After classifying the encounter, the analytical team must render an analytical judgment on their fused intelligence product using the guidelines found in Intelligence Community Directive (ICD) 203.³

E. Conclusion

UAP incident response requires collaboration among UAP organizations that focus on conducting rigorous and structured UAP research. UAP incident response requires involving subject matter experts from academic, government and private sectors who have the capability to conduct standardized UAP investigation and research efforts. UAP investigations are most effective by approaching evidence-based efforts through a collaborative model derived from the United States Department of Homeland Security National Incident Management System (NIMS)⁴. The overall objective of UAP strategic incident response is to determine the risk/threat proposition and render an analytical judgment regarding indicators of capability and intent that UAP presents. Analytical efforts should apply structured analytical techniques for intelligence analysis to best understand the characteristics and effects of UAP. The integration of standardized data collection, analysis and intelligence assessment will inform the best strategy for response to UAP.

³ Publicly available at <https://irp.fas.org/dni/icd/icd-203.pdf> (accessed 21 January 2025).

⁴ United States Department of Homeland Security, National Incident Management System Training Program, United States Department of Homeland Security, Washington D.C. (2011).

Author Biographies

Sean Grosvenor is a forensic consultant, retired from the Illinois State Police. Over his 25-year career, he served in various special assignments, including major crimes task forces, internal affairs, crime scene investigations and executive command. Sean is a court-qualified expert in bloodstain pattern analysis and firearms, and has testified in over 40 trials. He has provided training to over 50 public safety agencies in the areas of Sexual Assault, Crime Scene Management, Bloodstain Pattern Recognition, Search and Seizure, Forensic Photography, Arson Investigations, and Court Testimony. He is a graduate of the University of Illinois at Chicago and served as an adjunct instructor for the UIC Master of Forensic Science Program. Sean advises several organizations on investigative and intelligence assessment for the study of advanced non-human intelligence.

Keith Taylor, Ed.D is an adjunct assistant professor at John Jay College of Criminal Justice, has an extensive background in law enforcement and emergency management. His career spans various roles, including twenty-five years as a retired NYPD Sergeant Special Assignment and Assistant Commissioner for the NYC Correction Department. Dr. Taylor's expertise as a law enforcement professional includes Weapons of Mass Destruction response supervisor as well as a Planning Team Manager for FEMA Urban Search and Rescue New York Task Force 1. He is a graduate of Howard University, City College of New York, the Naval Postgraduate School, and Columbia University. He is an ASIS Certified Protection Professional, FEMA Master Exercise Practitioner, and IAEM Certified Emergency Manager.

Joshua S Pierson, MS, DSS is a strategic security subject matter expert and an Active-Duty US Army Chief Warrant Officer Four with 24 years in the field. Joshua has played a major role in educating his superiors and counterparts on the importance of technology protection, and insider threats, and illuminating adversarial capability and intent to target US and Allied Interests at home and abroad. Through his commitment to this role, he has helped increase the understanding of senior National Security and Intelligence Professionals regarding methodologies and models to counter adversarial interest in areas and venues of extreme sensitivity. He has a Bachelor of Arts in Intelligence Studies from American Military University, a Master of Science in Strategic Security and Protection Management from Henley-Putnam University, and a Doctorate in Strategic Security from National American University. Josh is the National Security Advisor to the Scientific Coalition for UAP Studies and the Society for UAP Studies.